

High Order Finite Element Schemes and Domain Decomposition Solvers for Large-scale Simulations in Electromagnetics

Emmanuel Agullo^a, Luc Giraud^a, Stéphane Lanteri^{b*}

Ludovic Moya^b, Jean Roman^a and Olivier Rouchon^c

^a*Hiepac project-team, Inria Bordeaux-Sud Ouest Research Center, Talence, France*

^b*Nachos project-team, Inria Sophia Antipolis-Méditerranée, Sophia Antipolis, France*

^c*CINES, Montpellier, France*

Abstract

We report on our work aiming at enabling large-scale simulations of frequency-domain electromagnetic wave propagation based on a recently developed innovative simulation software combining a high order finite element discretization scheme formulated on an unstructured tetrahedral grid, and scalable sparse linear solvers. The enabling numerical tool is a domain decomposition solution strategy for the sparse system of linear equations resulting from the spatial discretization of the underlying PDEs (Partial Differential Equations), that can be either a purely algebraic algorithm working at the matrix operator level (i.e. a black-box solver), or a tailored algorithm designed at the continuous PDE level (i.e. a PDE-based solver). The PDEs at hand here are the frequency-domain (or time-harmonic) Maxwell equations. Two concrete and different applications are considered for illustrating the modeling capabilities of the simulation software and assessing its parallel performances on the road to Exascale: the scattering of a plane wave by an aircraft, and the interaction of an electromagnetic wave with a heterogeneous model of head tissues.

1. Physical and application contexts

Electromagnetic devices are ubiquitous in present day technology. Indeed, electromagnetism has found and continues to find applications in a wide array of areas, encompassing both industrial and societal purposes. Applications of current interest include (among others) those related to communications (e.g. transmission through optical fibre lines), to biomedical devices (e.g. microwave imaging, micro-antenna design for telemedicine, etc.), to circuit or magnetic storage design (e.g. electromagnetic compatibility, hard disc operation), to geophysical prospecting, and to non-destructive evaluation (e.g. crack detection), to name but just a few. Equally notable and motivating are applications in defence, which include the design of military hardware with decreased signatures, automatic target recognition (e.g. bunkers, mines and buried ordnance, etc.) propagation effects on communication and radar systems, etc. Although the principles of electromagnetics are well understood, their application to practical configurations of current interest, such as those that arise in connection with the examples above, is significantly complicated and far beyond manual calculation in all but the simplest cases. These complications typically arise from the geometrical characteristics of the propagation medium (irregular shapes, geometrical singularities), the physical characteristics of the propagation medium

* Corresponding author email address: stephane.lanteri@inria.fr

(heterogeneity, physical dispersion and dissipation) and the characteristics of the sources (wires, etc.). In this study, we focus on the following application contexts:

- The first one relevant to engineering design in relation with industrial or defence applications. The goal here is to evaluate the RCS (Radar Cross Section) of an object (e.g. an aircraft). RCS is a measure of how detectable an object is with radar. RCS is used to detect planes in a wide variation of ranges. For example, a stealth aircraft (which is designed to have low detectability) will have design features that give it a low RCS (such as absorbent paint, flat surfaces, surfaces specifically angled to reflect signal somewhere other than towards the source), as opposed to a passenger airliner that will have a high RCS (bare metal, rounded surfaces effectively guaranteed to reflect some signal back to the source, lots of bumps like the engines, antennas, etc.).
- The second one deals with a societal application and is concerned with the evaluation of the potential effects of the interaction of microwaves with human tissues. The goal in that case is to evaluate the Specific Absorption Rate (SAR), which is a measure of the rate at which energy is absorbed by the human body when exposed to a radio frequency (RF) electromagnetic field. SAR measures exposure to fields between 100 kHz and 10 GHz. It is commonly used to measure power absorbed from mobile phones and during MRI scans. The value will depend heavily on the geometry of the part of the body that is exposed to the RF energy, and on the exact location and geometry of the RF source.

In the following we will not discuss further about RCS and SAR evaluation but instead concentrate on the core target problem that is shared by these two applications, which is concerned with the numerical solution of the system of frequency-domain (or time-harmonic) Maxwell equations for three-dimensional geometrical settings possibly involving heterogeneous media (e.g. biological tissues).

The work that we present here is concerned with the enhancement of the scalability properties of a simulation software whose development has started in the second half of 2014 at Inria. The simulation software named HORSE (High Order solver for Radar cross Section Evaluation) implements an innovative high order finite element type method for solving the system of three-dimensional frequency-domain Maxwell equations. From the computational point of view, a central operation of a HORSE simulation, which is the most expensive one indeed, is the solution of a large sparse and indefinite linear system of equations. High order approximation is particularly interesting for solving high frequency electromagnetic wave problems and, in that case, the size of this linear system can easily exceed several million unknowns. In this study, we have developed and experimented hybrid iterative-direct sparse system solvers based on domain decomposition principles: on one hand, a purely algebraic solver working directly on the system (i.e. matrix) coefficients, named MaPHYs, which can be considered as a black-box solver; on the other hand, a domain decomposition solver specifically designed at the continuous level for the system of frequency-domain Maxwell equations and further discretized in the considered finite element framework. For the numerical simulations and performance assessment of the enhanced version of the HORSE software we have used two computing systems: (1) a laboratory cluster equipped with Intel E5-2680@2.5 GHz nodes with 24 cores and 128 GB RAM per node, and an InfiniBand QDR TrueScale 40 GB/s switch interconnection; (2) the PRACE Bull/Atos system at CINES. Each node of this system is equipped with an Intel E5-2690 running at 2.6 GHz, with 24 cores on each node and 64 GB or 128 GB RAM per node.

2. Numerical approach

During the last 10 years, discontinuous Galerkin (DG) methods have been extensively considered for obtaining an approximate solution of Maxwell's equations. Thanks to the discontinuity of the approximation, this kind of methods has many advantages, such as adaptivity to complex geometries through the use of unstructured possibly non-conforming meshes, easily obtained high order accuracy, *hp*-adaptivity and natural parallelism. However, despite these advantages, DG methods have one main drawback particularly sensitive for stationary problems: the number of globally coupled degrees of freedom (DoF) is much greater than the number of DoF required by conforming finite element methods for the same accuracy. Consequently, DG methods are expensive in terms of both CPU time and memory consumption, especially for time-harmonic problems. Hybridization of DG methods is devoted to address this issue while keeping all the advantages of DG methods [7]. The design of such a hybridizable discontinuous Galerkin (HDG) method for the discretization of the system of 3d time-harmonic Maxwell's equations has only been considered very recently [2]-[8]

HDG methods introduce an additional *hybrid* variable on the faces of the elements, on which the definition of the local (element-wise) solutions is based. A so-called *conservativity condition* is imposed on the numerical trace, whose definition involved the hybrid variable, at the interface between neighbouring elements. As a result, HDG methods produce a linear system in terms of the DoF of the additional hybrid variable only. In this way, the number of globally coupled DoF is reduced. The local values of the electromagnetic fields can be obtained by

solving local problems element-by-element. In [2], for the system of 3d time-harmonic Maxwell's equations, we proposed an HDG formulation taking the tangential component of the magnetic field as the hybrid variable. We show that the reduced system of the hybrid variable has a wave-equation-like characterization, and the tangential components of the numerical traces for both electric and magnetic fields are single-valued. As will be illustrated in the results section of this paper, the approximate HDG solutions for both the electric and magnetic fields have optimal convergence orders.

3. Simulation software

HORSE is a computational electromagnetic simulation software for the evaluation of radar cross section of complex structures. This software aims at solving the full set of 3d time-harmonic Maxwell equations modeling the propagation of a high frequency electromagnetic wave in interaction with irregularly shaped structures and complex media. It relies on an arbitrary high order HDG method that is an extension of the method proposed in [2]. This HDG method designed on an unstructured possibly non-conforming tetrahedral mesh, leads to the formulation of an unstructured complex coefficients sparse linear system of equations for the DoF of the hybrid variable, while the DoF of the components of the electric and magnetic fields are computed element-wise from those of the hybrid variable [2]. This software is written in Fortran 95. It is parallelized for distributed memory architectures using a classical SPMD strategy combining a partitioning of the underlying mesh with a message-passing programming model using the MPI standard. One important computational kernel of this software is the solution of a large sparse linear system of complex coefficients equations. In a preliminary version of this software, this system was solved using parallel sparse direct solvers such as MUMPS [3] or PaStiX [4]. However, sparse direct solvers are in general poorly scalable when it comes to solve very large linear system arising from the discretization of 3d problems. In this project, we study the possibility of improving the scalability of HORSE by considering the use of hybrid iterative/direct solvers whose design is based on domain decomposition principles.

4. Enabling numerical tool: domain decomposition solver

Domain decomposition methods are flexible and powerful techniques for the parallel numerical solution of systems of PDEs. They can be used as a process of distributing a computational domain among a set of interconnected processors or, for the coupling of different physical models applied in different regions of a computational domain (together with the numerical methods best adapted to each model) and, finally as a process of subdividing the solution of a large linear system resulting from the discretization of a system of PDEs into smaller problems whose solutions can be used to devise a parallel preconditioner or a parallel solver. In all cases, domain decomposition methods (1) rely on a partitioning of the computational domain into subdomains, (2) solve in parallel the local problems using a direct or iterative solver and, (3) call for an iterative procedure to collect the local solutions in order to get the global solution of the original problem. Subdomain solutions are connected by means of suitable transmission conditions at the artificial interfaces between the subdomains. The choice of these transmission conditions greatly influences the convergence rate of the domain decomposition method. One generally distinguishes three kinds of domain decomposition methods:

1. Overlapping methods use a decomposition of the computational domain in overlapping pieces. The so-called Schwarz method belongs to this class. Schwarz initially introduced this method for proving the existence of a solution to a Poisson problem. In the Schwarz method applied to the numerical resolution of elliptic PDEs, the transmission conditions at artificial subdomain boundaries are simple Dirichlet conditions. Depending on the way the solution procedure is performed, the iterative process is called a Schwarz multiplicative method (the subdomains are treated sequentially) or an additive method (the subdomains are treated in parallel).
2. Non-overlapping methods are variants of the original Schwarz domain decomposition methods with no overlap between neighbouring subdomains. In order to ensure convergence of the iterative process in this case, the transmission conditions are not trivial and are generally obtained through a detailed inspection of the mathematical properties of the underlying PDE or system of PDEs.
3. Substructuring methods rely on a non-overlapping partition of the computational domain. They assume a separation of the problem unknowns in purely internal unknowns and interface ones. Then, the internal unknowns are eliminated thanks to a Schur complement technique, leading to the formulation of a problem of smaller size whose iterative resolution is generally easier. Nevertheless, each iteration of the interface solver requires the realization of a matrix/vector product with the Schur complement operator, which in turn amounts to the concurrent solution of local subproblems.

Two domain decomposition solution strategies are considered in this study: the first one works at the matrix operator level and combines the variants 1. and 3. in a purely algebraic way; the second approach is a variant 2. and is designed at the continuous PDE level by taking into account the intrinsic characteristics of the system of Maxwell equations.

4.1 MaPHyS algebraic solver

The solution of large sparse linear systems is a critical operation for many numerical simulations. To cope with the hierarchical design of modern supercomputers, hybrid solvers based on algebraic domain decomposition methods have been proposed. Among them, approaches consisting of solving the problem on the interior of the domains with a sparse direct method and the problem on their interface with a preconditioned iterative method applied to the related Schur Complement have shown an attractive potential as they can combine the robustness of direct methods and the low memory footprint of iterative methods. MaPHyS (Massively Parallel Hybrid Solver) [5]-[6] is a parallel linear solver, which implements this idea. The underlying idea is to apply to general unstructured linear systems domain decomposition ideas developed for the solution of linear systems arising from PDEs. The interface problem, associated with the so-called Schur complement system, is solved using a block preconditioner with overlap between the blocks that is referred to as Algebraic Additive Schwarz. To cope with the possible lack of coarse grid mechanism that enables one to keep constant the number of iterations when the number of blocks is increased, the solver exploits two levels of parallelism (between the blocks using MPI and within the treatment of the blocks using threads). This allows exploiting a large number of cores with a moderate number of nodes, which ensures a reasonable convergence behavior. MaPHyS makes use of PaStiX (Parallel Sparse matrix package) as a subdomain solver. The parallelization of PaStiX relies on a specific partitioning of the matrix blocks; the core operations in PaStiX are multithreaded allowing a second level of parallelization. PaStiX makes extensive use of highly optimized dense linear algebra kernels (e.g. BLAS kernels).

4.2 Schwarz solver based on PDE-compliant transmission condition

Alternatively to a purely algebraic approach such as the one adopted in MaPHyS, one can design a Schwarz algorithm at the continuous PDE level, which is then discretized using one of several possible finite element schemes including DG-type schemes. In [1] we proposed such an approach in the form of a Schwarz algorithm where Després type conditions are imposed at the interfaces between neighbouring subdomains. These conditions actually translate into a continuity condition for the incoming characteristic variables in the case of the first-order Maxwell system. This approach has been adapted to the HDG discretization framework in [2] but its implementation and numerical evaluation were limited to the case of a first order interpolation of the components of the electromagnetic field. In the present work, we further extended this PDE-based domain decomposition approach to an arbitrary high order HDG discretization method. The main advantage of the MaPHyS solver is that it is a black-box numerical tool and as such, it can theoretically be applied to any matrix system irrespective of the nature of the underlying PDE model. However, the main weakness of this approach is its possible lack of numerical efficiency because a Dirichlet interface condition is implicitly assumed, which can be suboptimal for certain PDEs. Devising a robust (and scalable) algebraic domain decomposition solver is still considered as a challenging research topic by the numerical linear algebra community.

5. Numerical and performance results

5.1 Computing systems

For the numerical simulations reported below we have used the following computing systems:

- The **Plafrim**[†] cluster at Inria Bordeaux – Sud-Ouest. Each node of this system is equipped with an Intel E5-2680 running at 2.5 GHz, with 24 cores on each node and 128 GB RAM per node. The interconnection network is an InfiniBand QDR TrueScale 40 GB/s switch.
- The **Occigen**[‡] Bull/Atos cluster at CINES. Each node of this system is equipped with an Intel E5-2690 running at 2.6 GHz, with 24 cores on each node and 64 GB or 128 GB RAM per node.

5.2 Plane wave propagation in vacuum

The first test problem that we consider is the simple problem of the propagation of a plane wave in a homogeneous domain. The computational domain is a unit cube, which is filled with vacuum. This problem can be used to validate the implementation of the HDG method and assess its accuracy and numerical convergence since an analytical solution exists. We do not discuss these numerical issues here and rather concentrate on

[†] <https://www.plafrim.fr/en/home>

[‡] <https://www.cines.fr/en>

computational performances and, in particular, on comparing the behavior of the various solution strategies previously described. The underlying tetrahedral mesh consists of 20,736 elements and 42,912 faces. In the figures and tables of this section and the following ones, «Pk» with $k=1,2,3,4$ denotes the order of the polynomial interpolation of the components of the electric and magnetic fields in each element (tetrahedron) of the mesh. Simulations for this test problem have been run on the Plafrim cluster.

Performance results are given in Figure 1 and Figure 2 for a strong scalability analysis of the various solution strategies. We evaluate different MPI processes/threads configurations, the multithreading capability being offered by the sparse direct solvers MUMPS and PaStiX. In all cases, the PDE-based Schwarz algorithm gives the lowest time to solution as it is clearly observed in Figure 2 on which we plot the elapsed time for the best MPI processes/threads for a given total number of cores. In general, the MaPHYs algebraic domain decomposition solver scales almost ideally (the ideal speedup is given by the dashed line in Figure 2). Not surprisingly, the solution strategy based on the sparse direct solver MUMPS (similar trends are observed with PaStiX) does not scale although it is somewhat competitive with MaPHYs from the time to solution point view, for the highest interpolation orders. We also observe that, for a given total number of cores, the best MPI processes/threads configuration is not the same for all the solution strategies. These results should be completed by an evaluation of the impact of multithreading on the memory consumption. This will be considered in the sequel of our study.

Figure 1: Plane wave propagation in a homogeneous domain.

Strong scalability analysis of simulations runs on the Plafrim cluster. «MaPHYs+MUMPS» and «MaPHYs+PaStiX» refer to MaPHYs with MUMPS and PaStiX as the subdomain solver respectively. On each plot, the various figures correspond to different configuration of subdomain partitioning (MPI parallelization) and threads within each subdomain. «MUMPS» corresponds to the case of sparse direct solver. «Schwarz+BiCGStab6» refers to the PDE-based Schwarz algorithm, which is here accelerated using a particular form of the BiCGStab Krylov method. We show several configurations in terms of number of subdomains and number of threads for a given total number of cores.

Figure 2: Plane wave propagation in a homogeneous domain.

Strong scalability analysis of simulation runs on the Plafrim cluster. «MaPHyS+MUMPS» and «MaPHyS+PaStiX» refer to MaPHyS with MUMPS and PaStiX as the subdomain solver respectively. On each plot, the various figures correspond to different configuration of subdomain partitioning (MPI parallelization) and threads within each subdomain. «MUMPS» corresponds to the case of sparse direct solver. «Schwarz+BiCGStab6 » refers to the PDE-based Schwarz algorithm, which is here accelerated using a particular form of the BiCGStab Krylov method. Here we show the best configurations in terms of number of subdomains and number of threads for a given total number of cores.

5.3 Scattering of a plane wave by an aircraft

We now consider a more realistic problem in the form of the scattering of plane wave by an aircraft. The unstructured tetrahedral mesh used for the simulations consists of 1,645,874 elements and 3,521,251 faces. The frequency of the incident plane wave is fixed to 600 MHz. A converged solution is obtained when using a third order approximation of the electromagnetic field components (for this particular mesh resolution). The size, in terms of numbers of DoF, for the discrete hybrid variable and electromagnetic field components are summarized in Table 1 for several polynomial interpolation orders in the HDG method. We present results of simulations performed using MPI parallelization mode only (combined MPI and multithreaded parallel execution mode will be considered in the future for larger problem sizes). These simulations have been performed on the Occigen system. Performance figures (strong scalability analysis) are given in Tables 2 and 3. We observe that the PDE-based Schwarz algorithm is the most efficient, and is scalable despite the increase of the number of iterations to convergence when increasing the number of subdomains. This numerical scalability issue with domain decomposition solvers is very well known. Appropriate strategies have been designed for symmetric positive definite systems in the form of so-called *coarse grid correction*. Such a correction has been recently introduced in the MaPHyS solver, however it cannot be exploited here in its current design because the matrix operator of the HDG hybrid variable system does not have the required mathematical property. Further investigation in that direction is required and is the subject of an on-going work. In the present context, the MaPHyS solver does not achieve the imposed accuracy threshold for the discrete HDG system based on second and third (not shown here)

order polynomial interpolation. This is the main cause of scalability degradation between the 768 and 1536 cores with the HDG-P1 method

HDG method	# DoF hybrid variable	# DoF EM field
HDG-P1	21,127,506	39,500,976
HDG-P2	42,255,012	98,752,440
HDG-P3	70,425,020	197,504,880

Table 1. Scattering of a plane wave by an aircraft. Number of degrees of freedom (DoF) of the discrete global and trace systems. The DoF of the hybrid variable are those that are globally coupled in the HDG trace system, which is solved using one of the proposed solution strategies: MUMPS, MaPHyS+PaStiX or PDE-based Schwarz+PaStiX. « # DoF EM field » is the total number of DoF of the discretized system for the components of the electric and magnetic fields.

HDG method	# Cores	# Iterations	Fact. Time	Sol. Time	Wall Time	Speedup
HDG-P1	384	3	2.6 sec	3.7 sec	6.8 sec	1.0
-	768	4	0.8 sec	2.3 sec	3.4 sec	2.0
HDG-P2	384	10	16.7 sec	40.5 sec	58.7 sec	1.0
-	768	12	5.1 sec	21.5 sec	27.1 sec	2.15
HDG-P3	768	23	18.8 sec	102.1 sec	122.6 sec	1.0
-	1536	26	5.1 sec	52.0 sec	58.7 sec	2.1

Table 2. Scattering of a plane wave by an aircraft. Strong scalability analysis on the Occigen system. PDE-based Schwarz solution strategy with PaStiX as a subdomain solver. « # Iterations » is the number of iterations of the Krylov solver (without preconditioning) used for the acceleration of the Schwarz algorithm, or a fixed threshold. « Fact. Time » is the maximum of the per subdomain factorization (LU factorization) time of the local problems. « Sol. Time » is the aggregate time for the application of the Krylov method. « Wall Time » is the total simulation time (used for the evaluation of the parallel speedup).

HDG method	# Cores	# Iterations	Fact. Time	Prec. Time	Sol. Time	Wall Time	Speedup
HDG-P1	384	93	26.3 sec	23.5 sec	21.5 sec	73.4 sec	1.0
-	768	194	7.2 sec	8.1 sec	18.6 sec	34.7 sec	2.1
-	1536	374	2.3 sec	2.5 sec	18.1 sec	23.5 sec	3.1
HDG-P2	768	5000	53.1 sec	55.2 sec	2353.0 sec	2463.0 sec	1.0
-	1536	5000	13.9 sec	16.4 sec	1243.0 sec	1276.0 sec	1.95

Table 3. Scattering of a plane wave by an aircraft. Strong scalability analysis on the Occigen system. MaPHyS solution strategy with PaStiX as a subdomain solver. « # Iterations » is the number of iterations of the preconditioned Krylov solver used for the resolution of the Schur complement system, for a fixed threshold. « Fact. Time » is the maximum of the per subdomain factorization (LU factorization) time of the local problems. « Prec. Time » is the maximum of the aggregate time for the application of the preconditioner. « Sol. Time » is the time for the application of the Krylov method to the Schur complement system. « Wall Time » is the total simulation time (used for the evaluation of the parallel speedup).

5.4 Interaction of an electromagnetic wave with biological tissues

We finally consider a test problem that allows demonstrating the capabilities of the HDG-based numerical methodology for dealing with electromagnetic wave propagation in heterogeneous media. The geometrical

model considered here consists of 4 tissues: the skin, the CSF, the skull and the brain. Each interface between two tissues is meshed separately before meshing the volume between the tissues, so that a highly conforming discretization of the interfaces is obtained. Recall that discontinuity of the electromagnetic field occurs at each interface. Each tissue is assigned specific values of the electromagnetic parameters (electric permittivity and electric conductivity). The final unstructured tetrahedral mesh used for the simulations consists of 361,838 elements and 725,136 faces. The size, in terms of numbers of DoF, for the discrete hybrid variable and electromagnetic field components are summarized in Table 4 for several polynomial interpolation orders in the HDG method. The frequency of the incident plane wave is fixed to 1800 MHz. Simulations have been performed on the Plafrim cluster. Triangulation of the skin and skull surfaces are shown on Figure 3, while contour lines of the amplitude of the electric field are plotted on Figure 4. The size, in terms of numbers of DoF, for the discrete hybrid variable and electromagnetic field components are summarized in Table 4 for several polynomial interpolation orders in the HDG method. A strong scalability assessment has been performed for the HDG-P1 and HDG-P2 method (see Figure 5), and considering various configurations of MPI processes/threads using MUMP as the subdomain solver of the PDE-based domain decomposition approach. We observe an almost linear speedup for the simulations based on the HDG-P1 method and, in some cases, a superlinear speedup when the HDG-P2 is used.

HDG method	# DoF hybrid variable	# DoF EM field
HDG-P1	4,350,816	8,684,112
HDG-P2	8,701,632	21,710,280

Table 1: Interaction of an electromagnetic wave with biological tissues. Number of degrees of freedom (DoF) of the discrete global and trace systems.

The DoF of the hybrid variable are those that are globally coupled in the HDG trace system, which is solved using the PDE-based Schwarz+PaStiX solver. « # DoF EM field » is the total number of DoF of the discretized system for the components of the electric and magnetic fields.

Figure 3: Interaction of an electromagnetic wave with biological tissues. Surface triangulations of the skin (left) and skull (right).

Figure 4: Interaction of an electromagnetic wave with biological tissues. Contour lines of the amplitude of the electric field.

Figure 5: Interaction of an electromagnetic wave with biological tissues. Strong scalability analysis on the Cluster system. PDE-based Schwarz algorithm with MUMPS as subdomain solver. Combined MPI/thread parallel execution mode.

6. Conclusion

Thanks to the leveraging of hybrid iterative-direct sparse system solvers based on domain decomposition principles, we have developed a new version of the HORSE simulation software with enhanced scalability properties and capabilities to address very large problems. HORSE is currently evolving in several directions with the goal of simulating a big challenge problem with several billion unknown on the order of 10,000 cores by the end of 2017.

The work presented here has potential links with the EoCoE (Energy Oriented Centre of Excellence):

- On one hand, the leveraging of advanced scalable numerical linear algebra black-box solvers such as MaPHyS is also considered in a task of the WP1 transversal workpackage in EoCoE work plan. As a matter of fact, in EoCoE, MaPHyS is further extended and exploited for several application domains. In MaPHyS has been integrated in the general purpose FEM CFD code « Alya » developed at BSC that is part of the application pillar workpackage on « Meteorology for Energy » and a scalability study will be scheduled during the first semester 2017. In addition, preliminary experiments on matrices provided by a partner from the workpackage on « Water for Energy » have been performed; the integration of MaPHyS in the corresponding simulation software is discussed to assess its efficiency at scale.
- On the other hand, innovative scalable DG-based solvers such as the one discussed here for the HORSE simulation software can also be exploited for the simulation of problems related to photovoltaic (more precisely, for the realistic numerical modelling light trapping in complex solar cell structures). As a matter of fact, a variant devised for the solution time-domain Maxwell equations is considered in a task of the WP1 transversal workpackage in EoCoE work plan, in close interaction with physicists from the IEK5 - Photovoltaik at the Forschungszentrum Juelich GmbH, in the context of an application pertaining to the application pillar workpackage on « Materials for Energy ».

References

- [1] V. Dolean, S. Lanteri and R. Perrussel. *A domain decomposition method for solving the three-dimension time-harmonic Maxwell equations discretized by discontinuous Galerkin methods*. J. Comp. Phys., Vol. 227, No. 3, pp. 2044-2072 (2008)
- [2] L. Li, S. Lanteri and R. Perrussel. *A hybridizable discontinuous Galerkin method combined to a Schwarz algorithm for the solution of the 3d time-harmonic Maxwell's equations*. J. Comp. Phys., Vol. 256, pp. 563-581 (2014)
- [3] P.R. Amestoy, I.S. Duff and J.-Y. L'Excellent. *Multifrontal parallel distributed symmetric and unsymmetric solvers*. Comput. Methods in Appl. Mech. Eng., Vol. 184, pp. 501-520 (2000)
- [4] P. Hénon, P. Ramet and J. Roman. *PaStiX: A high-performance parallel direct solver for sparse symmetric definite systems*. Paral. Comput., Vol. 28, No. 2, pp. 301-321 (2002)
- [5] L. Giraud, A. Haidar and L.T. Watson. *Parallel scalability study of hybrid preconditioners in three dimensions*. Paral. Comput., Vol. 34, pp. 363-379 (2008)
- [6] E. Agullo, L. Giraud, A. Guermouche and J. Roman. *Parallel hierarchical hybrid linear solvers for emerging computing platforms*. Compte Rendu de l'Académie des Sciences – Mécanique, Vol. 339, No. 2-3, pp. 96-105 (2011)
- [7] B. Cockburn, J. Gopalakrishnan and R. Lazarov. *Unified hybridization of discontinuous Galerkin, mixed, and continuous Galerkin methods for second order elliptic problems*. SIAM J. Numer. Anal., Vol. 47, No. 2, pp. 1319–1365 (2009)
- [8] N. Nguyen, J. Peraire and B. Cockburn. *Hybridizable discontinuous Galerkin methods for the time-harmonic Maxwell's equations*. J. Comp. Phys., Vol. 230, No. 19, pp. 7151–7175 (2011)

Acknowledgements

This work was financially supported by the PRACE project funded in part by the EU's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (2014-2020) under grant agreement 653838.